

A Novel Robust Fingerprint Identification System based on Hierarchical Indexing

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Abstract— Recent advances in technology have led to a wide range of systems which require reliable recognition schemes to determine the users identity. The goal of these schemes is to allow only authorized persons to use the service. Applications include secure access to computer systems, ATMs, buildings, laptops, mobile phones etc. This has led to the development of many biometric and fingerprint identification systems to confirm a person's identity. These systems are also used in forensics to identify criminals. Current fingerprint identification systems use texture and minutiae based features for identification but these approaches take too much time if one desires very good accuracy. Since accuracy and performance are a trade-off here this makes the problem very challenging. In this work we have developed a novel fingerprint identification system which uses a combination of SIFT features and a hierarchical structure to achieve both good accuracy and performance. First the SIFT features of images in the database are extracted in pre processing phase and stored. Then the query image is divided into regions and SIFT features of a particular region are extracted, then the query image is matched with the images in the database using the SIFT key points. The top N of the matching images are selected for the first level and rest of the images are ignored. The number N is currently selected heuristically. Then the same procedure is applied on the reduced database of images. SIFT features provide the system good accuracy and the hierarchical structure ensures good performance. The testing of the algorithm was done on a public domain database of real fingerprints. The proposed algorithm has a low query processing time which makes it efficient. Simulation and experimental results show that the proposed algorithm can accurately, robustly and efficiently be used for fingerprint identification. Also the algorithm is mostly insensitive to translation, rotation, displacement and noise in the fingerprints.

Keywords—*Biometrics & Authentication, Image/Video Processing and Coding, Image and Multidimensional Signal Processing, Bioimaging and Signal Processing, Image Processing & Understanding.*

Recent advances in technology have led to the widespread use of fingerprint recognition systems in many real life applications like Computer Network Logon, Electronic Data Security, E-Commerce, Internet Access, ATM, Credit Card, Physical Access Control, Cellular Medical Records, Distance Learning, etc. Most of the current systems for fingerprint use minutiae based features or global textures [2][9].The

goal of a fingerprint recognition system is given a fingerprint of a user the system has to identify the corresponding matching fingerprint in the database and thus identify the user. Recently [1] proposed the use of Principal component analysis and Line discrete Fourier transform to produce a fixed-length feature vector, which is invariant to translation, and in which rotation and scaling become translations.

But if the database is very large it makes the system very inefficient, since if one tries to go for a higher accuracy then the time taken for recognition increases considerably. Thus the time taken in recognition is a trade-off to the accuracy of the system. This inspired us to look for features which are translation, rotation and scale invariant.

[3] extended the existing technology of feature extraction and proposed a new fingerprint indexing and retrieval scheme using scale invariant feature transformation (SIFT) [4], which has been widely used in generic image retrieval[7][17]. With slight loss in effectiveness, they were able to reduce the number of features generated from one fingerprint for efficiency. To cope with the uncertainty of acquisition (e.g. partialness, distortion), they use a composite set of features to form multiple impressions for the fingerprint representation. In the index construction phase, they use locality-sensitive hashing (LSH) that allows for performing similarity queries by only examining a small fraction of the database.

Fingerprint indexing algorithms[8][15], which performs better than exclusive classification, select most probable candidates and sort them by the similarity to the input one. In [6], the triplets of minutiae and accessorial information are used in the indexing procedure. Even if some features are missing, the object fingerprint can still be retrieved as long as enough local features are found and matched.

The authors used reduced scale invariant feature transformation (SIFT) as a representation for fingerprint indexing. To cope with the drawback of using only one impression for indexing construction, they propose a method using composite local features[19].

In this work we propose a hierarchical indexing technique to expedite the image retrieval without compromising much on the accuracy of the system. In the Preprocessing stage SIFT features of all the databases are

computed and stored. Now when a query image comes it is divided into relevant regions as shown in fig 2 .Then the SIFT keypoints of region 1 are extracted and they are matched with the database images. The top matching images are shortlisted and form the reduced dataset of candidate images. The procedure is repeated for region 2 and region 3 and the final candidate list is obtained. The best matching image in the final candidate list is selected as the corresponding match for the query image and the person is thus recognized. Firstly, the system is run on the whole dataset using coarse grained features which take less time to compute and are not very accurate.

The hierarchy structure explained above is a 3 level structure. Number of levels could be changed depending on the size and quality of fingerprint database .

The fundamental advantages of this approach are:

1. It is a hierarchical pyramidal approach which filters out irrelevant images at each step and thus reduces the dataset.
2. It is fast, reliable and robust method for fingerprint identification without compromising on the identification accuracy.
3. If the system has difficulty identifying the last few (say 2 to 3) images with respect to the test image a human expert can see those images manually and find which the best match is.

I. APPROACH

There are four important modules of our Fingerprint recognition system which have the following tasks:

A. The pre-processing module

The task of this module is to register database images, extract its features and index them. An image from the database is taken, then it is broken up into various regions and the first level decomposition of the image is taken. SIFT features were extracted out of this decomposed image. Then a similar procedure was repeated for all the database images. Indexing of the Keypoints was done using k d tree [16] so that query for fingerprint recognition happens swiftly. The first level decomposed image is decomposed further to second and third levels and similar procedure is repeated to build a hierarchy of Indexes.

B. The Matching module

Given two indexed images from pre-processing module, the task of this module is to provide a score for the match of the images. The matching of SIFT Keypoints was done using Best-bin-first search method. The best candidate match for each keypoint is found by identifying its nearest neighbor from the keypoints of the database images. Euclidean distance was taken as the distance measure in finding the nearest neighbors. The ratio of distance from the closest neighbor to the distance of the second closest is taken as the probability of correct match.

Figure:1 (a) Original Fingerprint Image (b) SIFT Features of the fingerprint image.

All the matches which have a distance ratio greater than a thresholds are rejected, which eliminates most of the false matches while discarding only some correct matches.

For a pair of images I_1 and I_2 the matching module returns a matching score which in general represents the similarity between the images. The matching score (m) is calculated as follows:

$$m = p / \text{avg}(n_1, n_2) = 2p / (n_1 + n_2) \quad (1)$$

Where p is the number of matching SIFT keypoints in the two images I_1 and I_2 , n_1 is the number of SIFT keypoints in the image I_1 and n_2 is the number of SIFT keypoints in the image I_2 .

C. The Query module

Given a query image, the task of this module is to recognize the fingerprint. The query image is registered; its first level decomposition is done. Then the SIFT features of the decomposed image are extracted. The matching of these feature is done with the already indexed SIFT features of the first level decompositions of database images. The best N matches of the query image are shortlisted for the second level recognition process whereby the query image is decomposed again to second level and its SIFT features are extracted. Then the whole process of matching with the second level features of the database images are done on the reduced database of shortlisted images. A third level recognition can also be done similarly.

The best match finally is considered as the fingerprint of the recognized person and hence the person is recognized.

The hierarchical structure uses features of small image regions initially to reduce the candidate images in the database. At each level it continues to add more regions and reduce the set further until we are left with a small amount of potential candidates in which the recognition is run on full image. SIFT features provide the system good accuracy and the hierarchical structure ensures good performance. The testing of the algorithm was done on a library of real-life fingerprints from FVC2000 and FVC2002 database.

II. IMPLEMENTATION

The fingerprint recognition system using the approach defined above was run on the whole dataset using reduced

Figure:2 The different regions for decomposition,(a)First level (red) decomposition of a fingerprint,(b) Second level (green) decomposition of a fingerprint, and (c) Third level (blue) decomposition of a fingerprint.

SIFT features of only first level which take less time to compute and are not very accurate. The threshold to accept an image would be high in the first level. Time taken in level one was 460 seconds for a total of 500 images, making average time per image as 0.92 seconds. After first level only top 20% candidate images similar to the test image were shortlisted for the second level decomposition. Now the problem reduces to just identifying the test fingerprint from these 20% images (the reduced dataset). For second level time taken was 111 seconds for a total of 100 images, making average time per image as 1.11 seconds. Finally SIFT features of the entire query image are used to identify the query image within the smaller dataset. And for the final third level time taken was 26.5 seconds for a total of 25 images, making average time per image as 1.06 seconds. Thus total running time for completing all three levels becomes around 597.5 seconds, results for which are summarized in Table I. The hierarchy structure explained above is just a 3 level structure. Experiments were performed by dividing the image between two to five levels and the value of three was found to be best heuristically for this purpose as this makes a proper balance between accuracy and time complexity.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The system was implemented and tested in Matlab. Experimentation with FVC2000 and FVC2002 database showed us that for our problem the first two octaves in SIFT captured most of the important features of the fingerprint and higher order octaves have very little impact on the overall accuracy. Thus using fewer octaves (reduced SIFT features) we can reduce the length of the descriptor and thus the computation time for pre-processing and matching reduces

significantly. Also just taking six spatial bins suffices for the task and we can reduce the number of orientation bins to two for decreasing the descriptor length and thus accelerating the algorithm. Comparison between Minutiae, SIFT and Reduced SIFT with Multilevel Indexing approaches was done, results of which are summarized in Table II. It was found that Reduced SIFT with Multilevel Indexing approach performed well in terms of both matching time and penetration rate and is superior to other two approaches.

Figure:3 The fingerprint at different octaves and scale levels of the SIFT descriptor.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF ACCURACY AND TOTAL TIME FOR SIFT AND REDUCED SIFT FEATURES WITH MULTILEVEL INDEXING TO MINUTIAE BASED APPROACH.

Experiments	SIFT with Multilevel Indexing (Avg Time per Image)	Reduced SIFT with Multilevel Indexing (Avg Time per Image)	No. of Images selected to corresponding Level
Level 1	3.21 sec	0.92 sec	500
Level 2	3.82 sec	1.11 sec	100
Level 3	3.95 sec	1.06 sec	25
Total Time (in sec)	1605+382+98.75=2085.75	460+111+26.5=597.5	
Penetration rate	93.6 %	91.8%	

TABLE II. TIME TAKEN AND ACCURACY IN SIFT, REDUCED SIFT WITH MULTILEVEL INDEXING AND MINUTIAE WITHOUT INDEXING

Experiments	SIFT with Multilevel Indexing	Minutiae without any Indexing	Reduced SIFT with Multilevel Indexing
Time Taken in Pre - Processing	1906.7 sec	667.5 sec	1906.7 sec
Time Taken in Matching	2085.75 sec	482.5 sec	597.5 sec
Penetration rate	93.6 %	79.5 %	91.8%

Figure:4 Graph of Penetration rate v/s the number of candidate images.

IV. FUTURE WORKS

In this work we use SIFT features to represent the images. Other features and keypoint descriptors like SURF can be used to further improve the efficiency of the system. Moreover fusion with other biometrics can be done to improve the speed and reliability of the recognition system. It is also possible to combine the SIFT operator with other pattern based operations to improve the performance of system. More complex algorithms are also under consideration to improve the quality of SIFT keypoints suitable for fingerprint recognition.

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